

D6.8 Executive Summary

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Deliverable Information sheet

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Executive summary

This deliverable reports on the “VitiGEOSS Executive Summary”, which is a 19-page document highlighting the most relevant results of the project. The summary aims to translate the research and findings of VitiGEOSS to be more easily understood and useful for decision makers in the viticulture sector and beyond.

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1. Introduction

VitiGEOSS is a 42-month H2020-funded project aiming to promote the use of European open Earth observation (EO) services, and develop an innovative vineyard management tool based on the integration of EO, and in-field sensors to increase the resolution and reliability of satellite information applied to the viticulture sector.

The project responds to future challenges of the worldwide food and wine industry, which include the need to intensify the production in a sustainable way, mitigate the effects of climate change, reduce negative environmental externalities and promote local economic growth.

This deliverable reports on the “VitiGEOSS Executive Summary”, which is a 19-page report that presents the most relevant results of the project. The summary aims to translate the research and findings of VitiGEOSS to be more easily understood and useful for decision makers in the viticulture sector and beyond.

The target audience of the Executive Summary includes all project audiences, such as wine producers, viticulturists, technology and service providers, researchers, decision-makers, and the wider public.

2. Content

The executive summary begins with an **introduction** focusing on sustainable agriculture, the effect of climate change on the viticulture sector, and strategies for responding to the challenges faced.

The summary then presents the **VitiGEOSS project**, along with its vision, mission and services overview. Next, the **VitiGEOSS platform** is presented, with a quick user guide of the platform interface.

Subsequently, the report delves into the different **intelligent services**, what information they provide, and which data sources they use, as well as their potential application for decision making in viticulture. The concepts behind the services are expressed in a simple and easy-to-understand manner, thus translating them into a language easily digestible by non-experts.

An overview of the **pilots and co-production** approach used in the project is then described, followed by **testimonials** from the three end users on their involvement and experience in the project.

Finally, we conclude with a short **epilogue** and **resources** that readers can explore to find out more about the project, services and platform.

Figure 1. Front page and content list of the VitiGEOSS Executive Summary.

3. Format and publication

The VitiGEOSS Executive Summary is available in a 19-page booklet format as a PDF document, which was published in February 2024.

It includes text, images, plots, platform and intelligent service products (taken mainly as screenshots from the VitiGEOSS platform), and links (e.g. to the events and other material developed in the project).

The Summary is available in a dedicated section on the project website, title “Executive Summary” and found under the Results section. The Executive Summary will be widely promoted on social media, even beyond the project’s lifetime, to ensure a greater impact and potentially attracting future users of the commercial version of the VitiGEOSS platform.

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platform.vitigeoss.eu

PILOTS & CO-PRODUCTION

The platform developed in the VitiGEOSS project was validated at the pilot sites of three wine producers, involved in the project as end users:

- Mastroberardino in Irpinia, Italy
- Symington in Douro Valley, Portugal
- Torres in Catalonia, Spain

To ensure that the services developed in VitiGEOSS met the specific needs of end users, a co-production and user-centred design approach was adopted. This placed end users at the core of service design and development.

Through sharing their perspectives, knowledge and experiences, both researchers and users found common ground and learnt from each other, while ensuring the usefulness and usability of the VitiGEOSS services.

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THE VITIGE OSS SERVICES

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Weather & Climate Forecasts

Weather and climate conditions have a direct effect on the development of the cultivars, and information on the conditions is crucial to facilitate vineyard management. The Weather and Climate Forecast service offers information for the locations of the users' fields, covering three timescales: weather or short-term (next 3 days), sub-seasonal (next 4 weeks), and seasonal (next 3 months). Several variables are available, including temperature, maximum/minimum temperature, accumulated precipitation and shortwave radiation.

The sub-seasonal and seasonal climate forecasts are probabilistic, which means that rather than providing a specific value, they show the probability of the conditions falling within one of three categories. These categories are above normal, normal and below normal. The normal category is calculated based on observations from the past 30 years for the specific location and time of year. The probability of extreme conditions occurring is also marked in the graphs. When the forecast skill is low, the forecast is shown as 'uncertain'.

END-USER TESTIMONIALS

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Familia Torres is a family-owned winery with vineyards in Spain, Chile and California, founded in 1870, exporting premium quality wine and brandy to more than 100 countries.

The prospect of participating in the VitiGEOSS project was particularly fascinating because we saw the potential to significantly improve our management, by delivering tailored solutions that address the specific needs of our vineyards. We also were motivated by the opportunity to contribute to and benefit from a platform that promises to aid in vineyard management in ways that are not currently available on the commercial market.

Being involved in the co-production of the VitiGEOSS services has been an enriching experience for us. We embraced the opportunity to collaborate on a project that stands at the vanguard of viticulture technology, combining our knowledge of viticulture with sophisticated algorithms and geospatial data analysis. This initiative enabled us to use predictive modelling and estimation tools, embedding geospatial intelligence into our decision-making processes.

Working closely with the researchers was a highly positive and collaborative experience. The interaction with the research team was characterized by mutual respect. Despite occasional differences in perspectives, which are natural given by the diverse expertise of each party, we found these instances to be valuable in learning opportunities. They enabled us to broaden our understanding and approach to precision viticulture.

During the course of the project, we gained significant insights into the digitalisation of vineyards. We learned about the numerous ways in which digital tools and data analytics can enhance monitoring vineyard management.

We've found the platform to be intuitively designed, offering a user-friendly interface that simplifies the management and analysis of the vineyards. It provides clear and concise information, which is easily interpretable at a glance.

The service we find most useful is the parcel-level mapping visualization, particularly the NDVI (Normalized Difference Vegetation Index). It provides us with information regarding the homogeneity or heterogeneity of the vigor within the vineyard plot. This data has the potential to aid in the management of vineyard practices, including fertilization and irrigation strategies at a lower cost although less accuracy.

Figure 2. Examples of some pages from the VitiGE OSS Executive Summary.

4. Conclusion

This deliverable provides an overview of the VitiGE OSS Executive Summary, published in February 2024. The Summary highlights the most important aspects behind the research and advances of the VitiGE OSS project, and will serve as a reference for the project's success and achievements, ensuring the project legacy beyond its lifetime.